

New interactive front-end tools for visualizing and analysing data from quantitative and qualitative surveys: application to Crop Diversification Experiences across Europe

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Introduction

Temporal and spatial diversification of crops through rotation, multiple and intercropping schemes can improve farming systems efficiency, productivity and resilience, and thus sustainability. During recent years, farmers, scientists, advisors, private companies experienced crop diversification (CDE) all across Europe. These initiatives, how they are carried out and their outcomes, implies a wide diversity of parameters that are not easily taken into account by classical experimental approaches. During this conference, we propose a presentation of computer sciences tools developed for analyzing and visualizing data of various nature (qualitative, quantitative) collected to characterize european CDE.

Method

A two-fold survey was carried out in order to document CDE across Europe. The first part of the survey is based on a structured on-line questionnaire (LimeSurvey). One hundred-twenty-eight complete questionnaires were collected by partners of DiverIMPACTS project in 15 European countries. The collected data were mainly categorical (factors) and Likert-type scales. Results of this quantitative survey are reported in a parallel article (Drexler et al., this issue). Twenty-four CDE were then selected for the second part of the survey based on a qualitative approaches. Partners used an interview grid constituted by a limited number of open-ended questions for surveying various players/stakeholders of the selected CDE value chains.

Three tools were developed and used for analysing the data and visualizing the results of this two-fold survey. They rely on functions written in the R programming language at back-end in order to process the data, proceed with analyses and build graphs. The 'Shiny' R-package was used for building ShinyApps, as a front-end tool that interact with R back-end functions and data.

Results

Three tools will be presented during the conference and can be tested by attendees. These three tools are fully functional, but have a 'development' status, as new features are added based on users' needs. They are open-source and hosted on collaborative platforms (see section links to source code).

The first one is the R-package 'surveyvisualizr' which aims to visualize results of quantitative surveys (numerical, categorical, Liker-type data) through a ShinyApp running in a web-browser. The application will be used by the presenter or attendees in order to explore the results of the quantitative part of the survey on CDE across Europe (task 1.1), and more precisely to highlight main characteristics of initiatives, their main success and failure factors, and the major enablers and drawbacks they encountered.

The second one is the R-package 'qcoder' which aims to conduct qualitative coding of documents. This tool was initiated in May 2018 by international developers and was taken as a starting point for developing a relevant tool for applying the Cognitive Mapping Approach for analysing Systems of Practices (CMASOP, Vanwindekens et al. 2013) to transcribed qualitative interviews. Documents – such as transcribed interviews – are loaded, classed and qualitatively coded through a ShinyApp in a web browser. Practically, the researcher attribute directed relationships between two concepts of various natures to part of documents, typically sentence(s) or paragraph(s). This tool is used to process qualitative interviews of players from a variety of European CDE (task 1.2).

The third tool is the R-package 'cogmapr' which aims to treat the outputs of 'qcoder' in order to draw cognitive maps. Cognitive maps are digraphs of variables that can be used as a semi-qualitative model of interviewees' worldviews. The 'cogmapr' tool contains major functions from CMASOP: drawing Individual Cognitive Maps, computing Social Cognitive Maps and indicators from the graph theory. It works with a front-end ShinyApp shared as 'cogmapvisualizr' R-package. The 'cogmapvisualizr' application will be shown for exploring the results of the analyses of the qualitative interviews conducted among European CDE (task 1.2).

Conclusion

Recent developments done in the R community, particularly around R-studio and Shiny, allow scientists to build user-friendly and interactive front-end applications in order to treat, analyse and visualize data, by interacting with back-end R functions. During this conference, we present our experience with the development of three ShinyApps and their usage in DiverIMPACTS for documenting a sample of CDE in Europe. These tools and their concrete results could interest not only the scientific community, but also practitioners of crop diversification.

References

Vanwindekens, F., Stilmant, D. & Baret, P.V., 2013. Development of a broadened cognitive mapping approach for analysing systems of practices in social-ecological systems. *Ecological Modelling* 250 : 352–362

Links to source code & user manuals

- 'surveyvisualizr' <https://gitlab.com/FrdVnW/surveyvisualizr>
- 'qcoder' <http://github.com/ropenscilabs/qcoder>
- 'cogmapr' <http://frdvnw.gitlab.io/cogmapr/dev/>